

STEROID SAPOGENINS FROM INDIAN DIOSCOREA PLANTS. PART II

BY A. K. BARUA, * (Mrs) D. CHAKRAVARTI AND R. N. CHAKRAVARTI

Eleven different species of Indian Dioscorea plants, other than those already described in Part I, have been examined for the presence of saponin. It has been possible to isolate diosgenin in 3.35% yield from the yams of *Dioscorea deltoidea* by hydrolysis of the saponin. *D. deltoidea* is thus one of the richest source for this valuable steroid sapogenin.

In view of the importance of diosgenin as a valuable starting material for the preparation of steroid hormones including cortisone, it became desirable to carry out a chemical investigation of the yams of Indian Dioscorea plants. An account of the results obtained in the case of the yams of *D. alata*, *D. glabra*, *D. esculenta*, *D. oppositifolia*, *D. wallichii*, *D. pubera*, *D. prazeri* and *D. pentaphylla* was reported in Part I (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 173). Of the eight specimens of yams investigated, *D. esculenta* and *D. prazeri* yielded 0.17% and 2.1% of diosgenin respectively.

In the present communication an account of the results obtained in the case of eleven other yams of the Dioscorea family is being reported. These are *D. tomentosa*, *D. bulbifera*, *D. sativa*, *D. hispida*, *D. nummularia*, *D. beilophylla*, *D. aculeata*, *D. deltoidea* and unidentified species No. 1, 2 and 3. Examination of each individual specimen of yams was carried out following the same procedure as stated in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

D. tomentosa Koen, ex.Roxb. is a climber, twining to the left. The tubers grow in bunches, each one almost cylindrical throughout and about 10 cm. in length and 4 cm. in diameter with soft white edible flesh. Fresh yams contain about 72% of moisture. In the fractional solvent extraction, only the alcoholic fraction was found to contain traces of saponin.

D. bulbifera Linn. is a climber, twining to the left. Usually one yam grows per plant. It is globose in shape and has a purplish black skin, covered with a large number of feeding roots. Bulbils are abundant. When fresh, it contains about 68% of moisture. In the fractional solvent extraction, only the alcoholic fraction showed the presence of saponin in small amounts.

D. sativa Linn. is a climber, twining to the left. In this case, only the alcoholic fraction showed the presence of traces of saponin.

D. hispida Dennst. is a climber, twining to the left. The tubers are more or less depressed globose, often lobed, sparsely coated with small roots and are extremely poisonous. Occasionally, these are of considerable size, 30-35 kg. or larger still. Due

to its poisonous nature it is known in western India as *maraposhpoli* or deadly strangle cake. The Bhils poison tigers by placing powdered tubers in the carcasses of 'kills'. A piece of the size of an apple of this tuber is sufficient to kill a man within six hours. There is intense irritation of the mouth and throat, followed by a sense of suffocation and drowsiness and finally exhaustion. These are often taken by Santhals, Kols, Bhils and Paharias after removing the poisonous alkaloid by repeated washing with hot water.

Fresh yams contain about 55% of moisture. In the fractional solvent extraction, the alcoholic fraction contained traces of saponin, and the petroleum ether, ether and, particularly, chloroform fraction showed presence of sufficient amounts of alkaloid. The poisonous character of this yam is attributed to the alkaloid, dioscorine (Boorsma, "Meded. uitis. Lands. Plant, 1894, 13; Schutte, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1897, II, 130; Pinder and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2236).

D. nummularia Lam. is a climber, twining to the right. Fresh yams contain about 65% of moisture. Only the alcoholic fraction was found to contain traces of saponin.

D. aculeata Linn. is a climber, twining to the right. Usually one tuber grows per plant. The flesh is edible. The skin is often pink in colour. Fresh yams contain about 69% of moisture. None of the fractions contains any saponin.

D. deltoidea Wall. is a climber, twining to the left. The rhizomes are hard wood-like containing very little moisture and shaped like ginger. The skin is light yellow to chestnut-brown. Like *D. prazeri*, it is used by the Paharias (i) as an insecticide for removing lice from hair, (ii) as a soap for washing wool and silk and (iii) as a fish poison. In small doses it is used as a diuretic. The following are some of the Indian names, *kins, kildri, kithi, krithi, krits, krish* etc.

The rhizomes appear to contain 20% moisture. Both the ethyl acetate and alcoholic fractions were found to contain saponin, the proportion in the latter fraction being considerable. On working up in the usual way, as described in Part I, it gave 3.35% diosgenin, m.p. 204-206°; acetate, m.p. 194-95° and benzoate, m.p. 236-37°.

Unidentified Species

No. 1. It appeared to contain about 78% moisture. None of the fractions was found to contain any saponin.

No. 2. It was found to contain about 60% moisture. None of the fractions was found to contain any saponin.

No. 3. The yams were found to contain about 59% moisture. The alcoholic fraction was found to contain saponin in small amounts. Detailed work has not been possible for the paucity of the material.

Out of the nineteen different Indian yams investigated, *D. prazeri* of Darjeeling containing 2.1% and *D. deltoidea* of Kashmir, 3.35% diosgenin, are evidently two of the richest sources of this valuable raw material (Table I).

TABLE I

Diosgenin contents of plants of Indian and Foreign origin.

Name of plant.	Yield of diosgenin per 1000 g. dry yams.	Name of plant.	Yield of diosgenin per 1000 g. of plant.
Mexican Dioscorea:		American Trillium:	
<i>D. bulbifera</i> ...	4.5 g.	<i>T. declinatum</i> ...	5.0
<i>D. capillaris</i> ...	2.2	<i>T. erectum</i> ...	3.0
<i>D. composita</i> ...	3.0	<i>T. hugeri</i> ...	3.0
<i>D. cyphocarpa</i> ...	2.0	<i>T. ludovicianum</i> ...	5.0
<i>D. dugessi</i> ...	2.0	<i>T. recurvatum</i> ...	4.0
<i>D. galeottiana</i> ...	4.0	<i>T. simile</i> ...	4.0
<i>D. grandifolia</i> ...	1.5	<i>T. vaseyi</i> ...	0.4
* <i>D. hirsuticaulis</i> ...	1.5		
* <i>D. hirticaulis</i> ...	4.4		
<i>D. jaliscana</i> ...	3.1		
<i>D. lobata</i> ...	5.0		
<i>D. macrostachya</i> ...	2.9		
<i>D. mexicana</i> ...	3.9		
<i>D. militaris</i> ...	3.3		
<i>D. minima</i> ...	2.7		
<i>D. multinervis</i> ...	2.7		
<i>D. platycarpata</i> ...	3.0		
<i>D. plumifera</i> ...	4.1		
<i>D. pringlei</i> ...	3.5		
* <i>D. quartenata</i> ...	4.4		
<i>D. remotiflora</i> ...	3.7		
<i>D. subtomentosa</i> ...	4.4		
<i>D. testudinaria</i> ...	5.0		
<i>D. ulmet</i> ...	4.0		
<i>D. ureceolata</i> ...	4.6		
<i>D. composita</i> ...	12-30		
<i>D. villosa</i> ...	10-20		
		Mexican Balanites:	
		(per 1000 g. of pericarp of seed)	
		<i>B. aegyptica</i> ...	5.0
		Indian Balanites:	
		(per 1000 g. of dried yams)	
		<i>B. roxburghii</i> ...	1.0
		Indian Dioscorea.	
		<i>D. deltoidea</i> ...	33.5
		<i>D. esculenta</i> ...	1.7
		<i>D. prazeri</i> ...	21.0

* Undried yams used.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fractional extraction with various solvents.—Weighed amounts of the air-dried, powdered yams of different varieties of Indian Dioscorea plants were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°), ether, chloroform ethyl acetate and alcohol (90%). The

solvent of each fraction was evaporated and the residual products tested for the presence of saponin. The percentages of the solvent extracts from different solvents are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Name of the plant.	Pet. ether.	Ether.	CHCl ₃ .	HtAc.	EtOH	Total extract.
<i>D. tomentosa</i>	0.44%	0.71%	0.43%	1.05%	0.52%	3.15%
<i>D. bulbifera</i> (Indian)	0.41	0.55	0.58	1.27	1.61	4.42
<i>D. sativa</i>	0.46	1.43	0.37	1.85	0.99	5.09
<i>D. hispida</i> (Indian)	0.41	0.67	0.95	1.18	0.94	4.15
<i>D. nummularia</i>	0.53	0.78	0.54	1.35	3.23	6.43
<i>D. aculeata</i>	0.66	0.32	0.28	0.92	0.86	3.04
<i>D. deltoidea</i>	1.00	1.03	1.07	3.71	21.01	27.82
Unidentified species :						
No. 1	0.71	0.98	0.24	1.15	10.30	13.38
No. 2	0.67	0.66	0.28	2.92	1.44	5.97
No. 3	0.53	0.49	0.27	1.44	8.13	10.86

D. tomentosa Koen, ex. Roxb.—Only the alcoholic fraction was found to contain traces of saponin. It was not possible to isolate the sapogenin in any appreciable amount.

D. bulbifera Linn.—A small amount of saponin was found to be present only in the alcoholic fraction. The crude saponin fraction isolated from the yams, following the general procedure as described in Part I, on hydrolysis yielded a small amount of a solid mass which appeared to be a mixture of sapogenins. The constituents could not be separated due to the poor yield of the crude sapogenin fraction.

D. sativa Linn.—Only a small amount of the sample of the dry yams was available. In fractional solvent extraction only the alcoholic fraction showed the presence of saponin. No crystalline sapogenin could be isolated on hydrolysis of the saponin fraction.

D. hispida Dennst.—The alcoholic fraction was found to contain traces of saponin and the petroleum ether, ether and, particularly, chloroform fraction showed the presence of sufficient amounts of alkaloid. On account of the low yield isolation of the pure sapogenin was not possible.

D. nummularia Lam.—Examination of the various fractions showed the presence of traces of saponin in the alcoholic fraction. Due to low yield it was not possible to isolate the sapogenin in a pure state.

D. aculeata Linn.—No saponin was found to be present in fractional solvent extraction.

D. deltoidea Wall.—Both the ethyl acetate and the alcoholic fractions were found to contain considerable amounts of saponin, the proportion in the latter fraction being

much higher than that in the former. As regards isolation of the pure sapogenin, the method described in detail in Part I for isolation of diosgenin from *D. esculenta* and *D. prazeri* was adopted. The product obtained after crystallisation from absolute alcohol gave colorless needles of diosgenin, m. p. 204-206°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -128^{\circ}.7$ (CHCl_3), yield 3.35%. It was, however, observed that satisfactory yield could be obtained only when working with small amounts, say, 100 g. of the powdered rhizomes. While working with larger amounts, the extraction was not satisfactory and the yield of diosgenin often dropped down to even 1%. It gave no depression in mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of diosgenin. (Found: C, 78.4; H, 10.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_5$: C, 78.2; H, 10.1 per cent).

The *acetate* was obtained in the usual way by gently refluxing the pure sapogenin (0.1 g.) with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.25 c.c.) for half an hour. It crystallises in colorless needles from absolute alcohol, m. p. 194-95°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -119^{\circ}.5$ (CHCl_3). It gave no depression in mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of diosgenin acetate. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 9.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_6$: C, 76.3; H, 9.6 per cent).

The *benzoate* was obtained by dissolving the pure sapogenin (0.2 g.) in 2 c.c. pyridine. The solution on cooling was treated with a few drops of benzoyl chloride and kept overnight. It was worked up in the usual way when diosgenin benzoate was obtained in colorless needles, m. p. 236-37°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -81^{\circ}.5$ (CHCl_3). It gave no depression in mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of diosgenin benzoate. (Found: C, 78.7; H, 8.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_6$: C, 78.7; H, 8.9 per cent).

Among the three unidentified species examined, only in No. 3, the alcoholic fraction was found to contain sapouin in traces. As the yield was very low it was not possible to isolate the pure sapogenin.

The work was carried out in connection with the Enquiry on 'Dioscoreaceae' under the Indian Council of Medical Research during 1951-54.

Thanks are due to Dr. K. P. Biswas, Superintendent, and Dr. S. K. Mukherjee, Curator of Herbarium, Indian Botanic Garden, Calcutta, for identification of the plants.

DEPARTMENTS OF CHEMISTRY,
SCHOOL OF TROPICAL MEDICINE
AND
BETHUNE COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

Received January 16, 1956.